

Content Analysis of NIRF Ranked Law Institute's Library Websites of India: An Evaluative Study

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Abstract

India is well known and recognized as one of the reputed educational hubs in the world. The country is hosting a large group of students from diverse segments who are opting for higher education in various areas of studies. NIRF is ranking standard for evaluating higher learning system's performances and it regularly evaluates the country's higher learning platforms. Opportunity to study law in this country is wide and there are reputed institutes that are offering prosperous aspects to study the subject. However, the digital advance learning platforms are not sufficiently equipped with advanced technologies and facilities to support for remote and diverse student base. The present paper focuses on the content analysis on India's 2023-NIRF ranked law institute's websites to assess their standard and prospects of serving as globally validated online platforms. based on five best practices, namely, general information, Online resources, Online Law Resources, Search & Navigation and search functionalities, these portals are statistically evaluated. The research investigated the provision of library services and collections, as well as legal databases and resources that are accessible remotely, at the chosen institution. The information can be found on the websites of the libraries. The performance outcome reveals the websites as Above Average needing improvements in web-based technological features and online resources.

Keywords: Library website, content analysis, digital library, online higher learning, NIRF ranked digital law libraries.

1. Introduction

The Indian higher education structure is extensive and intricate. According to the most recent All India Survey of Higher Education Report (AISHE 2020-21), it is one of the most significant higher education sectors in the world. The country currently offers a total of 1,113 Universities, 43,796 Colleges and 11,296 Stand Alone Institutions as registered in AISHE 2020-21. Of them, 1,099 Universities, 41,600 colleges and 10,307 Stand Alone Institutions have filled and verified their responses”.

The study is designed and constructed to investigate and conduct an evaluation-based content analysis of the digital libraries at India’s law schools that are ranked highest by the NIRF in 2023.

2. The National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF)

In order to rank Indian higher education institutions, the Honourable Minister of Human Resource Development introduced the “National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF)” on September 29, 2015. Since then, the MHRD Minister has released a ranking list of Indian Institutions every year in the month of April.

India started its own rating system for Indian Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) based on Shanghai Rankings due to the subjectivity in the ranking methodology produced by QS World University Rankings and the Times Higher Education World University rating. The long-term goal of NIRF is to expand beyond ranking Indian HEIs and become a global league table. All government-run educational institutions are required to participate in NIRF as of 2018.

3. Literature Review

The study by Pal & Barman (2021) focuses on theoretical facets about different collections in a legal library. The study put a lot of emphasis on the function that librarians and the law library play in distributing legal knowledge. His research focused on the various sorts of law libraries in India and the users who frequent them.

Siddiqui & Khan (2017) emphasised the crucial elements a digital library needs in order to serve the wide range of students from all over the world. He claims that a digital library is a cutting-edge instrument for accelerating research and development for a company or a nation. However, creating a complete digital library is a difficult operation that calls for automation features to be used. According to the authors, users might quickly access the library website resources with the help of this function. A digital library requires top-notch information technology (IT) tools and other digital resources, they highlighted once more. Furthermore, a sizeable sum of money is required to buy the necessary technology and digital resources for the development of the digital library.

4. Conceptualization

4.1 Objective of the Study

The study intends to achieve the following goals through its evaluation and analysis as implemented in this research:

1. To evaluate NIRF Ranked 2023 Law Institutes Websites in India.

2. To conduct website content analysis making comparative evaluation on the Institute prospects and available online library features.
3. To compare the overall performances of the chosen institutes and evaluate the library standard and areas of improvements necessary for betterment of library infrastructure and students' learning assistance.
4. To find out the services and facilities provided on the websites.
5. To rank the selected institute library websites based on the score.

4.2 Scopes and limitations of the study

In this study India's 2023 NIRF-ranked top law institutes are chosen for the purpose of content evaluation of their available library websites. On that basis, National Law Institutes, a private law collage and an autonomous university is selected. Altogether nine (9) law institutes are chosen for the proposed comparison based descriptive evaluation out of 30th Institute. The table given below enlists all the chosen NIRF credited law institutes as ranked in NIRF 2023.

<https://www.nirfindia.org/Rankings/2023/LawRanking.html>

5. Methodology

In the present study the researcher has used both Google Chrome and Internet Explorer browser (to ensure website's browser compatibility) to locate and retrieve the most recent materials from the available library website of the chosen legal institute.

The study was divided into two categories: "Yes" and "No," and the scores are given as '1' and '0' respectively. A checklist-based observation method has been followed for this study. The MS-Excel utility is used for statistical computation. The collected data was prepared and presented in tabular form and calculated with simple calculation methods using Microsoft Excel.

Table 1: 2023-NIRF Ranking of the Law Institutes Selected for the Study and Their Score Comparison with 2022 Ranking

Sr. No.	Institute ID	Name	City	State	Score	2023 Rank	2022 Rank
1	IR-L-U-0238	National Law School of India University Abbreviation: NLSIUB Website: https://www.nls.ac.in/	Bengaluru	Karnataka	80.52	1	1
2	IR-L-U-0111	National Law University Abbreviation: NLUND Website: https://nludelhi.ac.in/	New Delhi	Delhi	73.91	2	2
3	IR-L-N-18	Nalsar University of Law Abbreviation: NULH Website: https://www.nalsar.ac.in/	Hyderabad	Telangana	73.76	3	4
4	IR-L-U-0585	The West Bengal National University of Juridicial Sciences Abbreviation: WBNUJSK Website: https://www.nujs.edu/	Kolkata	West Bengal	69.34	4	5

Sr. No.	Institute ID	Name	City	State	Score	2023 Rank	2022 Rank
5	IR-L-U-0134	Gujarat National Law University Abbreviation: GNLU Website: https://www.gnlug.ac.in/GNLU/Home	Gandhinagar	Gujarat	65.69	7	8
6	IR-L-U-0511	Dr. Ram Manohar Lohiya National Law University Abbreviation: DRRMLNLU Website: http://www.rmlnu.ac.in/	Lucknow	Uttar Pradesh	50.9	21	17
7	IR-L-U-0285	National Law Institute University, Bhopal Abbreviation: NLIUB Website: https://www.nliu.ac.in/	Bhopal	Madhya Pradesh	54.68	18	15
8	IR-L-C-19328	Symbiosis Law School Abbreviation: SLSP Website: https://www.symlaw.ac.in/	Pune	Maharashtra	66.67	6	3
9	IR-L-U-0500	Banaras Hindu University Abbreviation: BHUV Website: https://www.bhu.ac.in/	Varanasi	Uttar Pradesh	50.18	22	20

5.1 Data Collection

The investigator surfed through the NIRF website for the list of law institute. With the help of university websites homepages, investigator identified the library web pages of law institute for content analysis of library websites, a checklist was prepared for data collection. the checklist comprised of General Information, Online Resources, Online Law Resources, Search and Navigation, Assistance and Support. The investigator selected 09 law Institute library websites.

6. Content Analysis of the Library Website

After a thorough and systematic browsing and analysis (based on user interface, content, technical features, flexibility, web management and assistance) done on each library website of the selected law institutes, the findings are enlisted below in tabular format.

6.1 General Information of the Institute and Library

The table below shows the General Information in the official online library websites of the chosen 2023-NIRF certified law institutes. The information is collected by doing detailed home page study of the official library websites of the selected institutes.

Table-01 General Information

Sr. No.	General Information	NLSIUB	NLUND	NULH	WBNUJSK	GNLUG	DRRMLNLU	NLIUB	SLSP	BHUV
1	AboutUniversity	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	University History	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	About Library	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	Library Hours	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	Library Rules	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	Library Staff	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
7	News and Events	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
8	Membership	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
9	Library Map/Floor Plan	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
10	Visitor Info	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
11	FAQ	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
12	Contact	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
13	Copyright	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
14	NIRF Link	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
	Total (Out of 14)	12	11	9	13	13	11	10	11	13
	Percentage	85.71	78.57	64.28	92.85	92.85	78.57	71.42	78.57	92.85

The above table shows that WBNUJSK, GNLUG, and BHUV have scored over 90% in providing general information to users seeking online information about their respective law institutes and libraries. These institutes are leading in terms of comprehensive online information availability. Among the rest, NLUND, DRRMLNLU, and SLSP each have scores below 80%, indicating they provide less comprehensive information compared to the best-performing institutes. Specifically, NULH scored the lowest at 64.28%. Overall, the results are desirable and indicate that most institutes' websites are maintaining a good standard on this parameter.

6.2 Online Resources (e.g., books, journals, etc.)

The table below shows the online resources available in the web portals of the chosen 2023-NIRF certified law institutes.

Sr. No.	Online Resources	NLSIUB	NLUND	NULH	WBNUJSK	GNLUG	DRRMLNLU	NLJUB	SLSP	BHUV
1	E-Journals	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	E-Books	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	Manuscripts	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
4	E-Newspapers	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
5	Audio/Video/CD/DVD	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0
6	Legal Database	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
7	Maps	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
8	Back Volumes	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
9	Open Access E- resources	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
10	Print journals	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
11	Print Books	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
12	Microfilm	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total (out of 12)		7	7	8	9	9	8	9	9	8
Percentage		58.33	58.33	66.66	75	75	66.66	75	75	66.66

The above table shows that WBNUJSK, GNLUG, NLJUB and SLSP have more than 75% scores in providing online resources to users seeking information about their respective law institutes and libraries. Among the rest, NLUND, NULH, and BHUV (each below 70%) have scored equal to or below the aforementioned best-performing institutes. Overall, the result is desirable and can thus be inferred that the institutes' websites are maintaining a good benchmarking standard on this parameter

6.3 Online Law Resources

The table below shows the Online Law Resources available in the web portals of the chosen 2023-NIRF certified law institutes

Sr. No.	Online Law Resources	NLSIUB	NLUND	NULH	WBNUJSK	GNLUG	DRRMLNLU	NLIUB	SLSP	BHUV
1	SCC online	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	Law Finder	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Lexis Nexus Adv.	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
4	MANUPATRA	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	Competition Policy - International	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	J-GATE	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	JSTAR	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
8	World Trade Law	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	India stat	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
10	Kluwer Arbitration	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
11	Kluwer Patent law /IP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
12	Corporate law	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
13	South Asian Archive	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
14	West law Asia	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
15	AIR InfoTech	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
16	Hein Online	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
17	TAXMAN	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
18	Legit Quest	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0
19	Oxford Constitutional law	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
20	International Taxation	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
21	CLA/CDJ Law Journal	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
22	EPW	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1
23	PTCs	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total (out of 23)		12	11	12	11	11	9	8	13	3
Percentage		52.17	47.82	52.17	47.82	47.82	39.13	34.78	56.52	13.0

The above table shows that NLSIUB, NULH, SLSP have more than 52% scores in providing Online Law Resources to users seeking information about their respective law institutes and libraries. Among the rest, NLUND, WBNUJSK, GNLUG, DRRMLNLU, NLIUB and BHUV (each below 50%) have scored equal to or below the aforementioned best-performing institutes. Specifically, BHUV scored the lowest at 13.04. Overall, the result is desirable and can thus be inferred that the institutes' Online Law Resources are maintaining a good benchmarking standard on this parameter

Sr. No.	Assistance and Support	NLSIUB	NLUND	NULH	WBNUJSK	GNLUG	DRRMLNLU	NLIUB	SLSP	BHUV
5	New Arrival	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	Reprographic services	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
7	Scan and deliver	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Online Reading	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
9	Technical Support	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	DDS	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
11	Remote Access	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
12	Research Assistant	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total (out of 12)		8	7	6	6	8	6	7	6	7
Percentage		66.66	58.33	50	50	66.66	50	58.33	50	58.33

The table given above shows that NLSIUB and GNLUG have more than 60% score in providing learning assistance and support. Among the rest of the institutes, NLUND, NLIUB and BHUV (each below 60%) have scored equal and below the two top scoring institutes. The remaining three have 50% score each. Overall, the result does not meet global standardisation for higher educational websites and need further planning, policy development and rectifications.

7. Rank List of Websites under Study

The total score of each library website under study using the checklist technique has been presented in below, based on the previous table.

Name Of Institute	Table-1 General Information (Out of 14)	Table-2 Online Resources (Out of 12)	Table-3 Online Law Resources (Out of 23)	Table-4 Search and Navigation (Out of 09)	Table-5 Assistance and Support (Out of 12)	Score	Percentage	Rank
GNLUG	13	9	11	7	8	48	68.57	1
WBNUJSK	13	9	11	8	6	47	67.14	2
SLSP	11	9	13	6	6	45	64.28	3
NLSIUB	12	7	12	5	8	44	62.854	4
NULH	9	8	12	9	6	44	62.857	5
NLUND	11	7	11	7	7	43	61.42	6
DRRMLNLU	11	8	9	8	6	42	60	7
NLIUB	10	9	8	8	7	42	60	8
BHUV	13	8	3	8	7	39	55.71	9

The ranking of the university library websites under study based on the elements available on their website. Among all the libraries, 08 Libraries have scored more than percent out of 09. GNLUG has scored maximum among all the libraries, 48 (68.57%) out of 70 followed

by WBNUJSK-47 (67.14), SLSP-45 (64.28), NLSIUB-44 (62.854%), NULH-44(62.857%), NLUND-43 (61.42), DRRMLNLU-42(60%), NLIUB-42(60%), BHUV has scored -39(55.71%) Out of 70, least among all the libraries.

8. Discussion and Conclusion

8.1 Discussion:

With a score of more than 90%, it was found that the general information on the library websites portals of the best the law schools, including WBNUJSK, GNLUG, and BHUV, was accurate. This suggests that the general information provided by these institutions is comprehensive and well-organized, which is important for new users and anyone looking for general information about the library and its offerings. But in order to compete with other similar institutions like NULH—which obtained the lowest score in this category— need to improve their information dissemination to match their counterparts.

The accessibility of digital resources, such journals and e-books, is essential to any digital library. According to the survey, WBNUJSK, GNLUG, NLIUB, and SLSP overall performed very well, obtaining scores of more than 75%. According to this, these institutes offer an extensive library of online resources, which is important to helping researchers and students. NLUND, NULH, and BHUV, on the other hand, was a score below 70% and need to expand their digital collections to better serve their user base.

In general, performance was compared when it came to online legal resources. That institutions such as NLSIUB, NULH, and SLSP scored just over 50% indicates that there is a significant gap in the accessibility of specialised legal resources. With a poor 13.04%, BHUV shows a severe issue with the availability of sufficient online legal resources. In order ensure that students and scholars have access to the relevant legal databases, case laws, and statutes, this is an important issue that needs to be resolved immediately.

The navigation and search functions of library websites are essential for the user experience. NULH performed very well in this area, obtaining 100%, and was followed by WBNUJSK, DRRMLNLU, NLIUB, and BHUV, all of whom scored higher than 85%. This suggests that the search functions and interfaces of these institutes are easy to use. On another together, NLSIUB, which received the lowest score of 55.55%, has to improve the usability of its website in order to improve access to its resources.

Library help and support are critical for user happiness and effective library use. According to the survey, NLSIUB, NULH, and BHUV each scored 66.66%, showing that they provide sufficient help and support. This indicates a high standard of user support, which is necessary for assisting users and resolving problems. But NLIUB, which received the lowest score of 50%, needs to enhance its support offerings in order to properly cater to users' demands.

8.2 Conclusion:

The study's findings show that, if the digital library websites of India's leading law institutes show prospective, there are major possibilities for improvement. While the majority of institutes give suitable general information, there are sometimes insufficient internet resources available, particularly in the area of specialised law. There are notable differences in the user experience

between institutes, depending on how well or poorly their navigation and search functions work. In order to guarantee complete users pleasure, library support and help services also need to be improved.

To align with global standards, Indian law institutes must focus on the following recommendations:

1. **Optimise Search Features and Navigation:** To enhance user experience, include advanced, accessible search tools and simple navigation.
2. **Expand Online resources:** To assist academic and research endeavours, provide more e-books, journals, and particularly specialised legal resources accessible.
3. **Enhance Help and Support for Libraries:** Provide comprehensive user support services, such as live chat, extensive FAQs, and personalised help, to efficiently address the needs of users.
4. **Invest in Technology:** To improve resource accessibility and library operations, make use of cutting-edge IT tools and automated features.

By addressing these areas, Indian law institutes can significantly enhance their digital library platforms, providing better support to students and researchers and establishing themselves as global leaders in legal education.

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